

AN EVALUATION OF SERVICE QUALITY TOWARDS TOURIST ON HOP-ON HOP-OFF TOUR BUS SERVICE IN KUALA LUMPUR

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to evaluate how tourists respond to the service provided by Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. This study has incorporated with two objectives, namely 1) to assess the relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction, and 2) to determine the most influenced service quality attributes when using Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. SERVQUAL model has been adopted to assess the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. This study has employed descriptive survey from quantitative method where questionnaires were distributed to the users of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. 200 respondents were approached to have them evaluate the service quality while 151 questionnaires were qualified for data analysis stage by using SPSS ver. 24. The findings of correlation analysis have concluded that all five dimensions of service quality is positively correlated to customer satisfaction. Regression analysis has revealed that tangibility, reliability, assurance, and empathy are able to influence customer satisfaction significantly while responsiveness does not have significant influence towards customer satisfaction. Future research should emphasize on service quality gap between expectation and perception and also expand the research to Penang Island as Hop-On-Hop-Off service is also available.

Keywords: Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus, Service quality, Expectation, Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Transport activities remain necessary in tourism industry as they are responsible to enable tourists to travel or move from one place to another and thus allowing the successful development of new attractions (Rajamani & Rizal, 2013). It has been discussed in many tourism literatures that transportation influences tourist experience and attractiveness of destination in terms of availability and appropriateness of the usage by tourists. The influence of transportation is varied in countries where transportation in developed countries are assured while developing countries may be different because of diverse challenges, including service quality (Vilakazi & Govender, 2014). The relationship between transportation and service quality is highlighted as an important concern to the users in order to provide a better and comfortable environment so that the users are capable to travel around without obstacles (Zakaria et al., 2010). An effective and accessible public transportation network in a tourist destination is likely to attract more tourists to visit because if the transportation service has limited routes to travel around the destination, the users such as tourists or visitors may not be able to reach their desired destination especially independent travelers or drifters as their mobility depends on it (Bajada & Titheridge, 2017).

The development of transportation and growth of tourism are closely related to each other because the development of transportation is one of the major factors that supports the economic activity and visitors' movement. However, a more developed transportation infrastructure might have difficulties in meeting the needs of residents and visitors at the same time because different people have different needs and priorities. Although tourism activities will affect the demand in transportation, there is no direct relationship to show that the service quality of transportation will be improved (Albalate & Bel, 2010). Therefore, a well-planned transportation structure should be implemented to overcome the traffic congestion and urban sprawl.

Usually, transportation such as city buses, train and taxi are commonly used by people and it affects their travel decisions such as travel routes, modes, times, destination choices, ease, cost of travel, and qualities of the destination opportunities available for a particular trip (Bhattacharya et al., 2014). In Malaysia, buses are considered the most common public transportation as they are convenient and lower cost to travel. Taxis, on the other hand, are more expensive to travel as the fare is based on meter that calculates the distance from one destination to another. Train and light rail are well suited for trunk lines of public transport as

they provide a greater amount of passenger capacity compared to buses and also capable of transporting people without disturbance because they usually have their own lanes (City of Helsinki, 2015).

Problem Statement

A statistic provided by to the Department of Statistics Malaysia shows that the population up-to-date as of second quarter in 2018 is 32.4 million (Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia, 2018). As a multi-racial country, Malaysia consists of Bumiputera 61.9%, Chinese 18.9%, Indian 6.2%, and others 0.9% (Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia, 2018). The demand of transportation tends to increase according to the projected population growth. Public transportation in Malaysia has been growing steadily especially in Kuala Lumpur. Because there are many options of transportation to travel with, tourists often consider all the available options before choosing one. One of them is the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur where it usually caters for tourists to travel around Kuala Lumpur. However, congestion is one of the biggest concern because the tourists might not be able to reach their destination within the estimated time arrival and subsequently influence their perception and attitude towards visiting the destination (Chong, 2016). Complaints such as driver's attitude, cleanliness, safety, and comfort are also being raised up frequently as well.

The main issue of this research is to address the service quality influencing tourist satisfaction by adopting SERVQUAL model developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry in 1985 which consists of five dimensions, namely tangibility, empathy, responsiveness, reliability, and assurance. SERVQUAL is a model where it measures the quality of services on how a customer perceives from a service upon receiving it. The SERVQUAL model has also been examined by Handrinis et al (2015) where the model employs several dimensions to measure service quality. These dimensions were found to be reliable and are relevant in measuring service quality (Handrinis et al., 2015).

Research Objectives

1. To identify the service quality attributes that influence tourist satisfaction when using Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.
2. To assess the relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction.
3. To determine the most influenced service quality attributes when using Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

Research Questions

1. What are the service quality attributes that influence tourist satisfaction when using Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur?
2. Is there a relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur?
3. What is the most influenced service quality dimension when using Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur?

Research Framework

Figure 1.1 SERVQUAL Model (Adopted from Parasuraman et al, 1988)

Research Hypotheses

Five hypotheses have been established according to the research objectives above:-

H₁ There is a relationship between tangibility and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

H₂ There is a relationship between reliability and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

H₃ There is a relationship between responsiveness and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

H₄ There is a relationship between assurance and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

H₅ There is a relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

Significance of the Study

This study will contribute to the value of the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur and while it does not limit to it, it also can be used on Hop-On Hop-Off in other cities such as London, Paris, Sydney, and Rome. This study is able to reveal the current situation of Hop-On Hop-Off services in Kuala Lumpur so that this study should be able to retrieve information from respondents and improvise the service quality. Furthermore, this study is also able to assess out the importance of SERVQUAL model towards measuring tourist satisfaction level.

Limitation of the study

However, this study has limitation including time and cost. Upon completing proposal stage on deciding the topic of the study, this study was able to be carried out for three and a half months. Furthermore, this study concentrates on Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur and it requires the researcher to travel with the bus in order to acquire respondents. This limits the researcher in terms of sponsorship on the ticket cost, transportations fees, and questionnaire printing cost.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tourist

According to World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism is an economic, social, and cultural occurrence which requires the mobility of the individuals to place or countries apart from their normal living environment for either individual desire, business intention, or professional purpose. These individuals are tourists who stay for more than a day, or, are day-visitors. They can be international travelers or domestic travelers who are taking their holidays within their own countries. UNWTO defines a visitor where either domestic, outbound, or inbound is categorized as a tourist or some may call as overnight visitor if his or her trip includes an overnight stay. In a study performed by Pearce (1985), tourist has been identified with 9 role-related behavior, namely photographing, travelling to famous places, understanding local people, never really belonging, willing to participate in activities which involve physical contact, stopping by in a place for short period of time, willing to experiment with local food, language problem, and buying souvenirs.

Customer

A traditional definition of customer would be a person or someone who buys goods or services. According to Peppers and Rogers (2011), customers who can be identified as purchasers, buyers, or clients are part of the organization or as a whole either business-to-business (B2B) customers or end-user consumers. As explained by Ramees and Safeena (2016), customer is an important asset to any organization that he or she is expected to be given accurate and reliable information about the products or services offered or interested.

Satisfaction

Satisfaction is defined by Kotler and Keller (2011) where it is a pleasure or disappointment feeling of an individual perceived from the evaluation of perceived performance to expectations of a product. Ilieska (2013) stated that the definition of satisfaction has been established in common where satisfaction is the fulfillment response of consumer. The consumer may evaluate the product or service while the product or service might be providing or has provided the level of consumption-related fulfillment which can be high or low. However, Pizam and Ellis (1999) argued that satisfaction is not a common occurrence because not every individual receives the similar satisfaction from the same hospitality experience

because the expectations are influenced by people which their needs, intentions, and past experiences are different.

Customer Satisfaction

Barsky (1992) described customer satisfaction as a significant influence in service delivery because by understanding and satisfying the needs and wants requested from customers, it can stimulate the performance of market share from repeat purchases and recommendations to others. According to Alan et al. (2012), customer satisfaction is an evaluation of customers on a specific product or service that meets the needs and expectations of the customers. Atiyah (2017) stated that customer satisfaction is closely related to service quality where understanding the relationship is a requirement for organizations to have ability to compete and grow so that organizations are able to continuously provide high quality of service as a sustainable competitive advantage. Failure in meeting the needs and expectations would cause dissatisfaction of customers towards the product or service offered (Zeithaml et al., 2017).

Transportation in Tourism Industry

The importance of transportation has been strongly emphasized by many researchers in the past. Development of cities would be never be achieved if there is no transportation infrastructure because it allows people to reach to places with natural advantages for population concentrations which in return providing and trading good and services for economic specialization and efficiency (Khatri & Damodariya, 2015). Transportation is considered as a segment of the tourism component where it is responsible to bring tourists to destinations, go around the places, and leave the place when the trip is over (Sorupia, 2005). However, transportation in tourism should be treated as one of the important features of the tourism experience rather as a tool or medium (Halsall, 2001). In an urban tourism context, tourism products are usually made up from various goods and services where transportation is one of them (Thompson & Schofield, 2007). It is difficult to consider tourism without transportation as the process of travel and tourism experience of tourists together with tourism products starts and ends with transportation (Mammadov, 2012). Transportation accessibility should be provided especially for tourists and the connection of public transportation should be considered as a basic requirement towards the overall attractiveness and competitiveness of a tourism destination (Le-Klähn & Hall, 2014). A research done in

Tibet describes that the respondents would not have visited Tibet if there was no train service available (Su & Wall, 2009).

As defined by Hall in 1999, the provision of tourist dedicated transportation towards the enjoyment of destination and attraction is obvious as transportation service is often proposed as an attraction and utilized by tourists. In the earlier study, there are several characteristics that tourist dedicated transportation should have. The characteristics are, namely, it links the origin market with the tourist destination; it provides access and movement within a wide destination area in regional or country level; it offers access and movement within a tourist attraction; and it provides travelling service along a recreational route (Hall, 1999). Furthermore, even some of the urban public transportation services have their own tourist attractions, not because of the transportation service they offer but the transportation mode itself which have their own historical or heritage interest, or the views they offer over the city (Dubois & Aliaga, 2014). In the Master Plan and Development Strategy of the Croatian Tourism, transportation is incorporated with tourist experience where the service may offer service facilities near the road, airports and other passenger terminals which include information gathering, possibility of reservation, and sightseeing of roadside tourists' attraction. However, the patronage of transportation heavily depends on tourists' perception on how well the quality of transportation that the city has to offer. One example was given by a researcher where the reliability of the transportation, on-board cleanliness, security, and frequency influence customers' mind the most (Barabino et al., 2012).

As Albalate and Bel (2010) described, tourists arriving to destination or international cities would require mobility to move around place while some may hire private transportation, others may find it expensive. Because of this reason, public transportation infrastructure is necessary to satisfy the ones who may not afford to hire private vehicle such as bus, train, and taxi (Albalate & Bel, 2010). Transportation provided in a busy tourist destination indicates that the tourist attractions and other contents within the tourist destination are required by tourists which leads tourists to have a positive condition and pleasure to visit and stay in a certain destination (Kovačić & Milošević, 2016). The provision of transportation infrastructure should be performed by tourism stakeholders to increase the reliance on the infrastructure from central transportation hubs to transportation areas so that the tourist's attractions will be connected for ease of travel (Currie & Falconer, 2014).

Service Quality

As described by Zeithaml et al (2017), service quality is a critical element of customer perceptions. Maintaining service quality allows organization to obtain customer satisfaction (Agyapong, 2011). The attention towards service quality allows organization to differentiate itself from others and gain long term competitive advantage (Muhammad, 2017).

SERVQUAL

Tangibility

Tangibility refers to the things one can touch. In the context of the Tourism industry, these refer to the physical properties within a hotel and restaurants which provide the services for the guests and customers (Parasuraman et al., 1985). Tangibility can be divided into two categories which physical product and physical support (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1991). Physical product refers to the good that is consumed during the process of the service production while physical support refers to the framework that enables or facilitates the service production. According to Grönroos (2008), the concept of tangibility used to separate intangible services from their tangible counterparts has been focusing on the use of goods and services towards the consumer. The importance of tangibility has been emphasized as an important role because it helps to understand how consumer experiences are shaped (Hellén & Gummerus, 2013). The concept of tangibility also considers the cleanliness and the comfort that these equipment or properties which provide the services for the guests (Johnston, 1995). Tangible dimensions such as cleanliness and comfortable of physical facilities is able to influence the service quality of the public transportations (Zakaria et al., 2010). The cleanliness and comfort of the public transportations are seen in the interior of the train, the seats, windows, and waiting areas. Other examples of cleanliness are seen in the train, platforms, washrooms, lighting and air-conditioning in the train (Irfan et al., 2012). Tangible dimensions also represent the performance of the public transportation on its physical facilities such as interior, exterior, and engine of the public transportation (Bakti & Sumaedi, 2015). The authors further described that the dimension of tangible was measured by four indicators which were cleanliness of interior such as seats and windows; cleanliness of exterior look; and condition of the vehicle.

On the other hand, tangibility can also be referred to the physical facilities, professional appearance of staff and communication materials such as leaflets and brochures where they are very important to provide a complete educational experience during the ride

(Zeithaml et al., 2006). The importance of tangible factors is highlighted where it has great influence on customer loyalty and thus generate more profit to the organization (Alsaqre, 2011). A study also highlighted that tangible factors such as safety, cleanliness, comfort, sufficiency, and functionality of facilities provided at jetty terminal-type transportation are some of the factors that influence the level of satisfaction by its users (Abdullah et al., 2013). The authors conclude that the facilities provided should be maintained with a planned and systematic implementation of maintenance activity so that the facilities are able to operate at their best state and to be used for what they are built for. Maintenance such as updating or upgrading equipment and maintaining waiting areas cleanliness are some of the considerations which can be included in the perception assessment of input quality as they are some of the important inputs to produce good service to its users (Zakaria et al., 2010). Furthermore, a study shows that tangibility is proven to be a significant factor in influencing passengers' perception in a railway context where the changes of railway operation environment such as new station and advanced locomotive produce a good image of railway enterprises which indicate the passengers are satisfied in terms of tangible dimension (Jun & He, 2007). On the other hand, another study described that items in services capes model such as appearance of the employee and man-made physical environment surrounding the service can be identified as part of the tangibility dimension (Sureshchandar et al., 2002).

Reliability

Parasuraman et al. (1988) described reliability as the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. The definition of service reliability can be discovered in the earlier research where it is the ability of transit system to follow the schedule, to maintain regular development, and always have consistent travel time (Turnquist & Blume, 1980). In a transportation context, reliability is an important factor in determining the satisfaction level of passengers where the reliability level within an operation has an impact on the vehicle availability and subsequently affect the quality and quantity of the overall services (Mammo, 2010). The earlier research stated that reliability has come into an important characteristic of the service quality provided by transportation system and unreliable service in operations is a source of reduced productivity and increased costs for transit operators (Turnquist, 1981). The reliability of transportation infrastructure can be improved by implementing more and better information and communication technology (ICT) systems which improves communication with passengers, increases operational efficiency, lowers transaction costs, increases

productivity amongst internal employees, and results in positive perception of service (Vilakazi & Govender, 2014). Moreover, the reliability of transportation is deduced to be related in satisfying customers where attributes such as availability of transport, timely arrival of transport from and to, and notification of delays are much important to passengers (Horsu & Yeboah, 2015). A research stated that passengers using urban bus transportation services are very sensitive to waiting time and scheduled service where the transportation must operate exactly according to scheduled arrival and departure times by operating at the appropriate frequency (Iles, 2005).

Reliability is also about delivering promises and it is usually the most important determinant of perceptions of service quality where it includes the timeliness of arrival and departures times, and the consistency of service as is announced in the flight schedules itinerary, (Wilson et al., 2008). A study shows that improvements in reliable services are an essential service quality enhancement effort as a reliable service implies promise is being met on the attributes that the customers care about the service delivered to them (Govender & Naidu, 2011). This is supported by another study where reliability focuses on the frequencies and punctuality of the public transportation on arriving on time which results in meeting the perception and expectation of its users (Zakaria et al., 2010). The authors concluded that assessing the punctuality of public transportation provide positive impact towards the expectation and perception of customers although it has limited usefulness. A study has proven that punctuality is an important element in the reliability service quality of dimension in determining the satisfaction of the users where it is measured with arrival time and departure time (Thompson & Schofield, 2007). A punctual service provider is able to enhance the users' satisfaction level towards the quality of public transportation service (Bielen & Demoulin, 2007; Friman & Fellesson, 2009). Another study also described that the users were not satisfied with the reliability of the public transportation because the bus was not punctual in terms of destination arrival which influenced the expectation and perception towards the public transportation service provided (Eboli & Mazzulla, 2008). Hence, customers might switch to another organization if the service is not delivered in a reliable way which shows the organization is incompetent. An operation with poor reliability is subjected to several breakdowns such as limited number of buses on the route and poor scheduled service which will heavily influence the quality and quantity of the overall services (Mammo, 2010). A poor reliability in public transportation tends to drive away existing and potential passengers because the passengers might be influenced by the impact associated such as early or delay

arrival and extended waiting time which will elevate their discomfort and negative emotion towards the service (Bates et al., 2001; Rietveld et al., 2001).

Responsiveness

The earlier research defined responsiveness as speed and timeliness of service delivery where the service displays fast processing speed, prompt response to customer service requests, and minimal queuing time (Johnston, 1997). Responsiveness can be described as a reaction or presentation to what the consumer needs where organization may retain current customers and attract new customers in regards of environmental change if responsiveness is emphasized (Holweg, 2005). Responsiveness can be defined as the ability to provide prompt service all the time (Govender & Naidu, 2011). Another research also stated that ground airline staff should act responsively and responsibly wherever there are incidents like flight cancellation, flight delays, baggage loss, and emergency situations (Kim & Lee, 2011). In a full-service restaurant, the higher the responsiveness of the service is provided to the customers, the higher the satisfaction level of customer in which the customers would assume waiters to realize their needs and respond to them promptly (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006). The importance of responsiveness in service quality has been emphasized by Berry, Zeithaml, and Parasuraman (1985) where responsiveness is a key component in enhancing satisfaction and it is a major source of dissatisfaction if responsiveness is not included. Another study also stated that if responsiveness is not included in the service quality, this will cause bad perception from the consumers and thus the employees' behavior and consumer perception and satisfaction is closely related (Thompson & Schofield, 2002).

Responsiveness emphasized in attentiveness and promptness in responding customer requests, questions, issues, and complaints where these matters require communication towards customers by the waiting time they have to wait for assistance, answer to questions, or attention to problems (Zeithaml et al., 2017). When an organization is unable to attend the needs of customers for a certain period of time, it may result to negative perception of customers towards the service quality of the organization (Kaliannan et al., 2014). The authors emphasized that customers' needs should be attended at the first hand. In a transportation context, the responsiveness dimension in service quality is closely related to the attitude and behavior of the driver in public transportation which implies of the importance to evaluate service quality in the public transportation in regards of customer expectation and their perception (Zakaria et al., 2010). However, the perception of service quality will be

influenced by the types of interaction, either face to face or telephonically, the level of ability by service personnel to handle any matters arise effectively, and the degree of attention towards the requests demanded by customers (Blose & Tankersley, 2004). This can be supported by Zeithaml et al. (2017) where frontline employees are capable of directly influencing the responsiveness of customer perceptions through their individual willingness to assist and their timeliness in attending to customer's request. In health care industry, responsiveness can be enhanced by paying great attention to the recruitment stage of personnel based on their competency and perform continuous training of the employees which focuses on professional backgrounds and communication with patients (Purcărea et al., 2013).

Assurance

Assurance is defined as the knowledge and courtesy of the employees and the ability of the service provider and its employees to inspire customer trust and confidence (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Zeithaml et al., 2017). Assurance, as a broad dimension, consists of competence, courtesy, credibility, and security (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Grönroos (1990) further emphasized that assurance dimension will influences the overall perceived service quality where people is an important factor in providing services to others in regards of inseparability of service production and consumption, and also service co-production (Grönroos, 1990). However, the importance of assurance may not be relative to industries such as restaurant industry because of the risk and uncertain result upon using the service (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006; Zeithaml et al., 2017). Thus, for the medical and healthcare industry, banking, insurance, brokerage, and legal service, assurance dimension is an important factor that attract the attention of customers in assessing the ability of the firm in service production. The confidence and trust might be embodied into the employees who can relate their customers to the organization (Zeithaml et al., 2006). For that reason, whoever customers the individual employees interact will either confirm and build trust in the organization or ruin their trust although the reputation of the organization helps in enhancing service quality (Zeithaml et al., 2017). There is a strong possibility of customers not returning to the organization and have adverse effect on the organization if the customers are not comfortable with the employees because they are not able to deliver a better service which failed to inspire trust and confidence towards the customers (Liu et al., 2014). In a study performed in Ghana, assurance attributes such as attitude and behaviour of the driver and other public transportation staff are capable of determining customer perceptions of service

quality delivery (Nutsugbodo, 2013).

Furthermore, Setyowati (2016) studied about the innovation of service quality in bus transportation where the assurance dimension should include customer's feeling of being secure with the way the driver drives. A study of service quality also stated that assurance dimension has the most influence on service quality of transportation service which included the knowledge, attitude, and behaviour of drivers and also their ability to gain trust from their customers (Leonnard et al., 2017). In the first published SERVQUAL scale, the assurance dimension has 4 perception items to measure customer satisfaction, namely customer confidence affected by employee's behaviour, safe transactions with the organization, consistent courtesy from employees towards customers, and the ability of employees to respond to customer enquiries (Zeithaml et al., 2017). Ojo, Mireku, Dauda, and Nutsugbodo (2014) also investigated the service provided by local public transportations. The result showed that passengers were expecting with the assurance provided by the public transportation, but the end result was that the public transportations portrayed poor perception of service quality. Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler (2017) also stated that a guarantee is a pledge or assurance that a product or service offered by the organization towards the customers will be performed as promised. In another study on urban bus transportation service quality, customer satisfaction was low in assurance dimension where drivers and conductors were not well educated to behave courteously with the people, there were no fire and emergency exits on all buses, and also theft and crime activities were common on the buses (Verma et al., 2014).

Empathy

As defined by Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler (2006, p.120), empathy is the caring, individualized attention that the firm provides its customer. It is important for the customers to feel that they are unique and special and also their needs are expected to be understood by service providers (Zeithaml et al., 2017). Another literature explained empathy dimension as how an organization provides care and individualized attention to its customers in making them feel extra special and valuable which will be classified them as returning customers to the organization for the service (Liu et al., 2014). Leonnard, Comm, and Thung (2017) emphasized that empathy is an important variable in service quality which their study shows that the driver should provide caring and individual attention to the customers as it determines the level of customer satisfaction. Another study on public transportation shows that customers were not satisfied because of the omission of bus arrival information at certain stops, the font sizes of

information was too small, and the information provided was insufficient (Cheng et al., 2010). Mikhaylov, Gumenyuk, and Mikahylov (2015) described empathy dimension as the degree of sympathy and empathy of the driver or conductor to the issues of the passengers in the event of an emergency, an estimate on humanistic qualities of employees rather than their ability to follow orders. The study included several variables under empathy dimension such as disability assistance, compliance to customers' request in a traffic jam, optimal design of bus route, courtesy of waiting passengers who are running, and loyalty in an unforeseen situation (Mikhaylov et al., 2015).

A study performed by Sam, Hamidu, and Daniels (2018) shown that the perception and expectation of the customers have a large gap in terms of service empathy where the researchers believed that the transportation operators were not providing accurate services as expected and they were unable to personalize their service to cater the needs of individuals., Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler (2017) also stated that employees who have good relationship with customers, display emotional competence, display perceptive and attentive listening skills, and customer oriented will influence the customers to appraise better for the service they received and they are very likely to return for the service again. A study conducted by Phongsamran and Uttamang (2016) shown that the relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction was significant where the customers were receiving appropriate answer and solution from the employees which leads to high satisfaction level. In a restaurant context, employees who provide customers personal attention and proactively provide customers with quality service are excellent restaurants because these requirements help organizations to accumulate sustainable competitive advantage and value creation (Tzeng & Chang, 2011). Verma, Verma, Ajith and Sindhe (2013) stated that empathy dimension also extends to customer on improvement and adding new features to the services which are user friendly to the disabled individuals, young mothers, and also the safety of the passengers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this report is based on the quantitative research method. In using this method, hypotheses are formed, and the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable are tested to ascertain the validity of the hypotheses. A self-administered structured questionnaire will be used to collect the required data for analysis (Persaud, 2010; Creswell, 2003). The dependent variable used in this study is the tourist satisfaction on Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. The independent variables used are specifically found from the five dimensions of SERVQUAL from Parasuraman et al. 1985.

The final survey is conducted at Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur vehicles and stops along the route which covers the Golden Triangle of Kuala Lumpur. This was carried out in four weekends when more tourists can be found using this service. At the depot where the service ends, this is when most of the questionnaire were give out. This is the more appropriate time to evaluate the tourist experience with the service as they have just completed their rides. It was also worth mentioning that permission to conduct the survey was obtained from the Depot officials, and they were cooperative. The data collected were then analyzed by transferring manually to SPSS.

Sampling Design

While Hop-On Hop-Off service is available in both Kuala Lumpur and Penang, Kuala Lumpur has been chosen as part of this study. The target population of this study are tourists who have been travelling around Kuala Lumpur with Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service. The sampling frame can be found in the Tour Map of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service Kuala Lumpur. Non-Probability sampling technique is carried out, and every tourist had an equal chance of being surveyed. A total of 200 forms was distributed. From this, 151 questionnaires were accepted for analysis. The others were not considered as the answers were incomplete. The sample size of this study was 200. As mentioned above, the number of samples collected was 151 at the end of four-weekend survey.

Data Collection

Primary Data

Primary data are data that are collected firsthand for the specific research problem at hand by using procedures that fit the research problem at best. The sources of primary data can be from self-administered survey, interviews, field observation, and experiments (Persaud, 2010). For this study, self-administered questionnaire has been selected in order to gather a significant amount of data at a relatively little cost (Beiske, 2002). Self-administered questionnaire is useful in data collection as it is efficient to administer since many people are able to fill in the questionnaires at the same time and respondents are independent to answering questions which biasness is reduced (Bryman & Bell, 2007). However, self-administered questionnaire consists of several drawbacks where response rate could be low and questions in the questionnaires might not be answered completely which is invalid to the data analysis.

Secondary Data

Secondary data are data that are collected by someone else where it can be on other research or studies whether they are related or unrelated to the original research (Boslaugh, 2010). Secondary data can be referred to books, journals, news, internet, and academic research.

Questionnaire Design

This research is regarding on how tourists react to the service provided by Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. Self-administered questionnaire was adopted, and the questionnaire structure is divided into Section A, Section B, and Section C.

Section A describes about the demographics of the respondents such as nationality, gender, age, educational level, employment status, and who do they travel with. Section B consists of items about the independent variables. Statement 1 to 3 measures the tangibility aspects of the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur while statement 4 to 6 measures the reliability aspects. The responsiveness dimension is assessed from statement 7 to 9 while the assurance attributes are measure from statement 10 to 12. The final part of Section B consists of statement 13 to 15 which measures the empathy dimension. A structured questionnaire was created based on previous research and has adopted the five-point Likert scale to describe the items in relation to five SERVQUAL dimension (Parasuraman et al., 1988) which begins from 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and ends with 5

= Strongly Agree for all the questions involved in this study. The questions in Section B were designed with closed-ended questions for timesaving, easy for comparison, tabulation, and analysis. Section C consists of the dependent variable on the overall satisfaction level.

Drop-off method is used for the self-administered questionnaire in the data collection process. The respondents were asked to fill out the questionnaire during the ride and at bus stops in Kuala Lumpur. There were 200 questionnaires distributed to the respective respondents and 151 questionnaires were collected, which has the response rate of approximately 75.5%. The respondents usually spent five to six minutes to complete the questionnaire given in average. The data collection process has taken two days to complete, and two tickets have been purchased to perform the data collection.

Variables	Dimensions	Indicators
Service quality	Tangibility	1. Bus station and facilities are comfortable. 2. Buses have spacious and comfort seats. 3. Interior and exterior of bus, facilities, and equipment are clean and hygienic.
	Reliability	1. Ticketing and billing services are consistent. 2. Buses are punctual in terms of departure and arrival. 3. Safety and security service are reliable.
	Responsiveness	1. Bus companies provide specific time and efficient service. 2. Communication with staffs is clear and helpful. 3. Staffs are always willing to serve you.
	Assurance	1. Driver and conductor are consistently courteous and polite with the passenger. 2. Driver and conductor are knowledgeable. 3. Driver obeys to careful driving style.
	Empathy	1. Bus companies give a convenient operating hour. 2. Staffs understand your specific needs. 3. Bus companies give special care for women, children, and handicap.
Customer Satisfaction	Customer satisfaction	1. Overall, Kuala Lumpur Hop-On Hop-Off meets my expectation. 2. My overall experience with Kuala Lumpur Hop-On Hop-Off was good and I would recommend it to my friends.

Table 1.2 Measurement of Independent and Dependent Variables

Data Analysis

Data analysis will be conducted after the field data collection is completed. There are several software packages that can be used for statistical tools. However, Statistical Package for the Social Scientist (SPSS) was chosen as part of the data analysis as it is user friendly and understandable user interface. The data collected will then be analyzed by the Statistical Package for the Social Scientist (SPSS) software version 24. Upon the analysis, the result will then be presented in the statistical form and clear explanation. Descriptive statistics of the results on demographics such as frequency distribution and mean calculation will be presented in table forms. Independent variables and dependent variable will be analyzed by using factor analysis, descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	75	49.7
	Female	76	50.3
Age	Below 20	11	7.3
	21 to 30	39	25.8
	31 to 40	35	23.2
	41 to 50	34	22.5
	51 to 60	17	11.3
	61 and above	15	9.9
Education	High school	16	10.6
	Undergraduate	89	58.9
	Postgraduate	46	30.5
Employment	Student	28	18.5
	Employed	84	55.6
	Unemployed	26	17.2
	Retired	13	8.6
Travelling partner	Alone	4	2.6
	With friends	23	15.2
	As a couple	44	29.1
	With family	80	53

Table 1.3 Demographic Information of Respondents

There were 200 questionnaires distributed, filled out and 151 out of 200 were accepted for further analysis, at a response rate of 75.5%. In terms of gender, the respondents are categorized into 75 male and 76 female which is almost equally distributed. The biggest age group in this study was 21 to 30 years old which occupied 25.8% of the total respondents, followed by 31 to 40 years old at 23.2%, 41 to 50 years old at 22.5%, 51 to 60 years old at 11.3%, 61 years old and above at 9.9%, and lastly below 20 years old at 7.3%. Respondents who have undergraduate qualification dominated a huge percentage of the total respondents at 58.9% while postgraduate respondents occupied 30.5% and high school respondents was the minority group at 10.6%. In terms of employment status, 55.6% of the respondents are employed, 18.5% of the respondents are students, 17.2% of the respondents are unemployed, and lastly 8.6% of the respondents have retired from their employment. A total of 53% of the respondents were

travelling with their family while 29.1 of the respondents were travelling as a couple. 15.2% of the respondents were travelling with their friends while only 2.6% of the respondents were travelling alone.

Factor analysis

Dimensions	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Factor Loading
Tangibility	TAN1	2.95	1.022	0.820
	TAN2	3.29	1.087	0.890
	TAN3	3.79	1.093	0.685
Reliability	REL1	3.74	1.016	0.752
	REL2	2.68	1.061	0.856
	REL3	3.89	0.850	0.778
Responsiveness	RES1	3.42	0.859	0.623
	RES2	3.80	0.857	0.905
	RES3	3.95	0.893	0.908
Assurance	ASS1	4.18	0.817	0.837
	ASS2	3.78	0.856	0.831
	ASS3	4.07	0.713	0.702
Empathy	EMP1	3.60	0.888	0.797
	EMP2	3.36	0.868	0.858
	EMP3	2.95	0.807	0.720

Factor analysis helps to identify each factor as representing a specific theoretical factor, reduce the number of variables, and determine the appropriate number of factors (NCSS Statistical Software, 2018). A principal component analysis with varimax was performed and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling measurement adequacy is 0.822, which is considered adequate for factor analysis output as Taherdoost, Sahibuddin, and Jalaliyoon (2014) suggested that Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) above 0.6 to 0.7 is appropriate for factor analysis. The significance of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity in this study was 0.000 which was below 0.05. Chan and Idris (2017) suggested that the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity must be significant at $p < 0.05$ to confirm the relationship of the variables in the data. Both tests have proven that factor analysis is appropriate. Above table shows that all the values of factor loading are greater than 0.3.

Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.866	.867	15

Table 1.5 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha is one of the most used measurement to examine the internal consistency of a test which can be expressed as a number between 0 and 1 (Pallant, 2007). Tavakol and Dennick (2011: 53) stated that the internal consistency describes the extent to which all the items in a test measure the same concept or construct and hence it is connected to the inter-relatedness of the items within the test. Pallant (2007) suggested that values above 0.7 are considered acceptable while values above 0.8 are preferable. The Cronbach's Alpha scale reliability test for this study has calculated a value of 0.866. The reliability value in this study indicates that the statements produced according to the five dimensions of SERVQUAL are appropriate for further analysis.

Items	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Bus station and facilities are comfortable.	50.50	56.838	.525	.482	.857
Buses have spacious and comfort seats.	50.17	55.179	.595	.575	.853
Interior and exterior of bus, facilities, and equipment are clean and hygienic.	49.67	57.383	.446	.376	.862
Ticketing and billing services are consistent.	49.72	57.018	.516	.362	.857
Buses are punctual in terms of departure and arrival.	50.77	55.896	.564	.514	.854
Safety and security service are reliable.	49.56	59.008	.478	.427	.859
Bus companies provide specific time and efficient service.	50.04	58.585	.505	.310	.858
Communication with staffs is clear and helpful.	49.66	58.334	.528	.656	.857

Staffs are always willing to serve you.	49.51	57.865	.538	.703	.856
Driver and conductor are consistently courteous and polite with the passenger.	49.28	58.149	.574	.485	.855
Driver and conductor are knowledgeable.	49.68	58.701	.499	.436	.858
Driver obeys to careful driving style.	49.38	60.198	.476	.312	.859
Bus companies give a convenient operating hour.	49.86	59.281	.431	.407	.861
Staffs understand your specific needs.	50.09	57.498	.586	.576	.854
Bus companies give special care for women, children, and handicap.	50.51	60.345	.397	.296	.862

Table 1.6 Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted

According to Table 1.6, shows that 15 statements were measured individually on the reliability scale and the impact of the scale if one item is to be deleted from it. The value of Cronbach's Alpha in this study does not change much when an item is deleted as all the items showed a lower value of reliability than the alpha value. Pallant (2007) recommended that items that are higher than the final alpha value should be removed if final alpha value is less than 0.7.

Dimension	Items	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha for dimension	Cronbach Alpha if item deleted
Tangibles	TAN1	3	0.717	0.621
	TAN2			0.448
	TAN3			0.777
Reliability	REL1	3	0.709	0.677
	REL2			0.500
	REL3			0.654
Responsiveness	RES1	3	0.750	0.881
	RES2			0.528
	RES3			0.517
Empathy	ASS1	3	0.703	0.529
	ASS2			0.545
	ASS3			0.727
Assurance	EMP1	3	0.705	0.617
	EMP2			0.487
	EMP3			0.714

Table 1.7 Cronbach's Alpha for Dimensions

Table 1.7 presented the reliability scale for each dimension and when each item is deleted from each dimension to show the importance of the deleted item. There are 10 items of all five dimensions shown reliability coefficients of less than 0.7. Pallant (2007) stated that it is difficult to achieve a decent Cronbach's Alpha value for scales with a small number of items which has three items in each dimension in this study. In other words, the number of items influences the Cronbach's Alpha value.

Results and Analysis of Research Objectives

Descriptive Analysis

Tangibility of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur

Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
Bus station and facilities are comfortable.	10.6	19.9	35.8	31.1	2.6	2.95	1.022
Buses have spacious and comfort seats.	9.9	10.6	27.8	43.7	7.9	3.29	1.087
Interior and exterior of bus, facilities, and equipment are clean and hygienic.	2	13.2	20.5	32.5	31.8	3.79	1.093

Key: SD-Strongly Disagree, D-Disagree, N-Neutral, A-Agree, SA-Strongly Agree, M-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation

The table shows that 35.8% of the respondents were neutral to the statement that the bus station and facilities are comfortable while 31.1% of the respondents agreed, 19.9% of the respondents disagreed, 10.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed, and only 2.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with a mean of 2.95 and standard deviation of 1.022. In terms of seat space and seat comfort of the bus, majority (43.7%) of the respondents agreed, 27.8% of the respondents stayed neutral, 10.6% of the respondents disagreed that the buses have spacious and comfort seat, 9.9% of the respondents strongly disagreed, and only 3.29% of the respondents strongly agreed with a mean of 3.29 and standard deviation of 1.087. For the cleanliness and hygiene of the interior and exterior of bus, facilities, and equipment, 32.5% of

the respondents agreed while 31.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 20.5% of the respondents stayed neutral, 13.2% disagreed, and only 2% strongly disagreed on the statement with a mean of 3.79 and standard deviation of 1.093.

Reliability of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur

Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
Ticketing and billing services are consistent.	2	9.9	25.8	36.4	25.8	3.74	1.016
Buses are punctual in terms of departure and arrival.	17.9	23.2	31.8	27.2	0	2.68	1.061
Safety and security service are reliable.	0	2.6	33.8	35.1	28.5	3.89	0.85

Key: SD-Strongly Disagree, D-Disagree, N-Neutral, A-Agree, SA-Strongly Agree, M-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation

The table shows that 36.4% of the respondents agreed to the statement that the ticket and billing service are consistent while 25.8% of the respondents strongly agreed and another 25.8% of the respondents stayed neutral, 9.9% of the respondents disagreed, and only 2% of the respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.74 and standard deviation of 1.016. In terms of the arrival and departure punctuality of buses, 31.8% of the respondents stayed neutral, 27.2% of the respondents agreed that the buses are punctual for arrival and departure. However, 23.2% of the respondents disagreed and 17.9% of the respondents strongly disagreed which indicates the buses failed to meet their expectation with a mean of 2.68 and standard deviation of 1.061. For the safety and security service of the buses, 35.1% of the respondents agreed while 33.8% of the respondents remain neutral, 28.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 2.6% disagreed, and there were no respondents who strongly disagreed with the statement with a mean of 3.89 and standard deviation of 0.85.

Responsiveness of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur

Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
Bus companies provide specific time and efficient service.	1.3	13.9	33.1	45	6.6	3.42	0.859
Communication with staffs is clear and helpful.	0	4.6	34.3	37.1	23.8	3.8	0.857
Staffs are always willing to serve you.	0.7	3.3	28.5	35.8	31.8	3.95	0.893

Key: SD-Strongly Disagree, D-Disagree, N-Neutral, A-Agree, SA-Strongly Agree, M-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation

The table shows that 33.1% of the respondents agreed to the statement that the bus company provide a timely and efficient service while 33.1% of the respondents remain neutral, 13.9% of the respondents disagreed, 6.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, and only 1.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.42 and standard deviation of 0.859. In terms of communicating with the staff, majority (37.1%) of the respondents agreed that the communication was very clear and helpful, 34.3% of the respondents stayed neutral, 23.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, only 4.6% of the respondents disagreed, and there were no respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.8 and standard deviation of 0.857. For the willingness of the staff to serve the passenger, 35.8% of the respondents agreed that the staff was willing to serve them while 31.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 28.5% of the respondents remain neutral, a tiny 3.3% of the respondents disagreed, and only 0.7% strongly disagreed on the statement with a mean of 3.95 and standard deviation of 0.893 which shows that the customers were satisfied of being served by the staff.

Assurance of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur

Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
Driver and conductor are consistently courteous and polite with the passenger.	0	2.6	17.9	38.4	41.1	4.18	0.817
Driver and conductor are knowledgeable.	1.3	2	35.8	39.1	21.9	3.78	0.856
Driver obeys to careful driving style.	0	2	15.9	55	27.2	4.07	0.713

Key: SD-Strongly Disagree, D-Disagree, N-Neutral, A-Agree, SA-Strongly Agree, M-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation

The table shows that a huge percentage at 41.8% of the respondents strongly agreed to the that the driver and conductor are consistently courteous and polite with the passengers while 38.4% of the respondents agreed, 17.9% of the respondents remain neutral, only 2.6% of the respondents disagreed, and there were no respondents strongly agreed with the statement, leaving a mean of 4.18 and standard deviation of 0.817. In terms of the knowledge of the driver and conductor, majority (39.1%) of the respondents agreed, 35.8% of the respondents stayed neutral, 21.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that the driver and conductor are knowledgeable, 2% of the respondents disagreed, and only 1.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.78 and standard deviation of 0.856. For the driving style of the driver, 55% of the respondents agreed that the driver was careful and act in the customers' best interest while 27.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, 15.9% of the respondents stayed neutral, only 2% disagreed, and no respondents strongly disagreed with the statement, achieving a mean of 4.07 and standard deviation of 0.713.

Empathy of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur

Statements	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
Bus companies give a convenient operating hour.	0	11.9	31.8	41.1	15.2	3.60	0.888
Staffs understand your specific needs.	0.7	13.2	45.7	29.8	10.6	3.36	0.868
Bus companies give special care for women, children, and handicap.	5.3	16.6	58.9	16.6	2.6	2.95	0.807

Key: SD-Strongly Disagree, D-Disagree, N-Neutral, A-Agree, SA-Strongly Agree, M-Mean,
 SD-Standard Deviation

The table shows that 41.1% of the respondents agreed that Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur provides convenient operating hours to its customers while 31.8% of the respondents remain neutral, 15.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, 11.9% of the respondents strongly disagreed, and there were no respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.6 and standard deviation of 0.888. In terms of provision of specific needs by the staff, majority (45.7%) of the respondents remain neutral, 29.8% of the respondents agreed, 10.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that the staff understands specific needs from the passengers, 13.2% of the respondents disagreed, and only 0.7% of the respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.36 and standard deviation of 0.868 which is close to neutral response from the respondents. For special care provided for women, children, and handicap, a high percentage at 58.9% of the respondents remain neutral on the statement while 16.6% of the respondents agreed and another 16.6% disagreed, 5.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed, and only 2.6% strongly agreed on the statement with a mean of 2.95 and standard deviation of 0.807.

Pearson Correlation Analysis

		TAN	REL	RES	ASS	EMP	SAT
TAN	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	151					
REL	Pearson Correlation	.588**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000					
	N	151	151				
RES	Pearson Correlation	.382**	.405**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000				
	N	151	151	151			
ASS	Pearson Correlation	.391**	.404**	.543**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000			
	N	151	151	151	151		
EMP	Pearson Correlation	.368**	.349**	.431**	.495**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		
	N	151	151	151	151	151	
SAT	Pearson Correlation	.671**	.654**	.513**	.606**	.565**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	151	151	151	151	151	151

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Key: TAN-Tangibility, REL-Reliability, RES-Responsiveness, ASS-Assurance, EMP-Empathy, SAT-Satisfaction

The Pearson correlation in Table 4.12 shows that the five dimensions of SERVQUAL model were moderately correlated with the overall satisfaction. One-tailed test is selected as it tests a directional hypothesis which is according to the hypotheses developed in this study (Field, 2009). All the relationships were positive and significant. Tangibility has a 0.671 correlation with overall satisfaction which falls under the coefficient range from ± 0.30 to ± 0.70 which is moderate. The positive correlation indicates that tangibility and overall satisfaction vary in same direction where higher level of tangibility will result higher level of overall satisfaction. The p-value of 0.000 is below of alpha value 0.01 and it indicates the relationship between tangibility and overall satisfaction is high. A 0.654 correlation of reliability with overall satisfaction indicates that there is a positive relationship where higher value of reliability will result better overall satisfaction. A 0.513 correlation of responsiveness with overall satisfaction indicates that there is a positive relationship where higher level of responsiveness will result higher level overall satisfaction. The p-value of 0.000 is below of

alpha value 0.01 and it indicates the relationship between responsiveness and overall satisfaction is high. A 0.606 correlation of assurance with overall satisfaction indicates that there is a positive relationship where higher level of assurance will result higher level overall satisfaction. The p-value of 0.000 is below of alpha value 0.01 and it indicates the relationship between assurance and overall satisfaction is high. A 0.565 correlation of empathy with overall satisfaction indicates that there is a positive relationship where higher level of empathy will result higher level overall satisfaction. The p-value of 0.000 is below of alpha value 0.01 and it indicates the relationship between empathy and overall satisfaction is high. Overall, the variable “tangibility” has the strongest correlation with the “overall satisfaction” variable ($r = 0.671$, $p < 0.01$), followed by “reliability”, “assurance”, “empathy”, and “responsiveness” ($r = 0.654$, $r = 0.606$, $r = 0.565$, and $r = 0.513$, $p < 0.01$, respectively).

Multicollinearity Analysis

Independent Variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Tangibility	0.608	1.645
Reliability	0.601	1.663
Responsiveness	0.636	1.573
Assurance	0.595	1.680
Empathy	0.692	1.445

According to the table above (Table 4.13), the tolerance value ranged from 0.595 to 0.692 while the values in VIF (variance inflation) were ranged from 1.445 to 1.680. The general rule of thumb described Multicollinearity is accepted where tolerance value should be higher than 0.1 corresponding to a VIF of maximum at 10 (Hair et al., 2009).

Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.828 ^a	.685	.674	.19355

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Reliability, Responsiveness, Tangibility, Assurance

Multiple regression analysis is an analysis to assess the relationship between one continuous variable and a number of independent variables or others may call as predictors (O'Brien & Scott, 2012). A standard multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between service quality dimensions of the SERVQUAL model that affect customer satisfaction of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. As shown in Table 4.12, the predictors of empathy, reliability, responsiveness, tangibility, and assurance have reached 67.4% (R Square = 0.685) of the variation in the customer satisfaction Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur which indicates 67.4% of customer satisfaction was explained by the independent variables. Moreover, the relationship strength between the independent variables (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) and the dependent variable (tourist satisfaction) is at 82.8% (R = 0.828).

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.810	5	2.362	63.052	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.432	145	.037		
	Total	17.242	150			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy

The ANOVA analysis shows that $F(5, 145) = 63.052$ is significant at $p = 0.000$, indicating that constructing regression model is consistent with the collected data and the predictors are statistically significant at the 5% significance. Therefore, the predictors for the independent variables in the model are related to the dependent variable.

Multiple Linear Regression

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.975	.112		-8.712	.000
	Tangibility	.126	.024	.317	5.309	.000
	Reliability	.120	.026	.275	4.575	.000
	Assurance	.125	.032	.232	3.840	.000
	Empathy	.105	.028	.210	3.746	.000
	Responsiveness	.030	.028	.064	1.090	.277

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Table 1.8 Regression analysis of five dimensions of SERVQUAL and customer satisfaction

To further examine the five dimensions that influence the overall satisfaction of tourists, all five dimensions were employed together in a multiple regression analysis. Multiple regression analysis was employed because it provides an accurate interpretation of the independent variables as a whole in relation to the dependent variable. As shown in Table 4.16, all five independent variables were presented in beta coefficients of the standardized factor scores. The significant factors for the five dimensions in the regression analysis were presented according to the significance of beta coefficient. The dependent variable, overall satisfaction level of tourists was measured on a dichotomous scale with the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.

According to Table 4.16, Dimension 1 (Tangibility, $\beta_1 = 0.317$, $p = 0.000$) was established to have a significant positive relationship with overall tourist satisfaction with the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur, followed by Dimension 2 (Reliability, $\beta_2 = 0.275$, $p = 0.000$), Dimension 4 (Assurance, $\beta_4 = 0.232$, $p = 0.000$), and Dimension 5 (Empathy, $\beta_5 = 0.210$, $p = 0.000$). However, Responsiveness dimension was found to be the least important variable in the regression model ($\beta_2 = 0.064$, $p > 0.05$). Thus, the relationship was not statistically significant.

Discussion of the Results

Results of the Hypotheses

Hypotheses	Results
H ₁ There is a positive relationship between tangibility and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.	Supported
H ₂ There is a positive relationship between reliability and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.	Supported
H ₃ There is a positive relationship between responsiveness and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.	Supported
H ₄ There is a positive relationship between assurance and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.	Supported
H ₅ There is a positive relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction in the Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur.	Supported

Table 1.9

Tangibility

According to the data analysis above, tangibility has a significant and positive relationship with overall customer satisfaction. With reference to the result from Pearson correlation analysis, tangibility displayed a correlation of 0.671 with the overall customer satisfaction which indicates a relationship with moderate strength among other dimensions. With the reference to the result from multiple linear regression analysis, tangibility displayed a coefficient of 0.317 which indicates there is a positive and significant relationship between tangibility and overall customer satisfaction. The data analysis concludes that tangibility is the most influencing dimension in assessing customer satisfaction when all other dimensions are accounted for.

The result is associated with the findings by Liu and Gao (2007) where tangibility is more important in determining customer satisfaction than reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness. A study by Irfan et al. (2012) also stated that tangibility has the most significant impact on customer satisfaction among the independent variables. Zakaria et al. (2010) described that tangibility will influence the service quality of transportation which is able to determine the level of customer satisfaction. Oyeobu et al. (2014) also stated that tangibility has a strong relationship with customer satisfaction where higher tangibility in service quality will lead to better customer satisfaction.

Reliability

According to the data analysis above, reliability has a significant positive relationship with overall customer satisfaction. With reference to the result from Pearson correlation analysis, reliability displayed a correlation of 0.654 with the overall customer satisfaction which indicates a relationship with moderate strength among other dimensions. With the reference to the result from multiple linear regression analysis, reliability displayed a coefficient of 0.275 which indicates there is a positive significant relationship between reliability and overall customer satisfaction. The data analysis concludes that reliability is the second most influencing dimension in assessing customer satisfaction when all other dimensions are accounted for.

The result is associated with the findings by Horsu and Yeboah (2015) where reliability has a significant and positive relationship with customer satisfaction. A study by Vilakazi and Govender (2014) stated that reliability significantly influence the overall service quality of transportation. As described by Hoffman and Bateson (2006), reliability is an important dimension to the customers because customers are able to determine from their past experience whether the organization is trustworthy or not when it comes to delivering their promises to the customers. A study by Mammo (2010) stated that reliability is one of the major discouraging factors in resulting dissatisfied customers. Hence, high reliability will result in better customer satisfaction.

Responsiveness

According to the data analysis above, responsiveness has a significant positive relationship with overall customer satisfaction. With reference to the result from Pearson correlation analysis, responsiveness displayed a correlation of 0.513 with the overall customer satisfaction which indicates a relationship with moderate strength among other dimensions. With the reference to the result from multiple linear regression analysis, responsiveness displayed a coefficient of 0.064 which indicates there is a positive but insignificant relationship between responsiveness and overall customer satisfaction where the p-value is greater than 0.05. The data analysis concludes that responsiveness is the least influencing dimension in assessing customer satisfaction when all other dimensions are accounted for.

The result is inconsistent with a study performed by Sam et al. (2018), Lwesya and Jaffu (2017), Demir et al. (2015), So et al. (2006) which stated that responsiveness dimension is the most influential variable in customer satisfaction in transportation yet the result in this study has revealed that responsiveness is the least influential variable in assessing customer satisfaction. The result can be supported by a study conducted by Mudenda and Guga (2017) where responsiveness dimension of service quality was deemed to have less significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Assurance

According to the data analysis above, assurance has a significant positive relationship with overall customer satisfaction. With reference to the result from Pearson correlation analysis, assurance displayed a correlation of 0.606 with the overall customer satisfaction which indicates a relationship with moderate strength among other dimensions. With the reference to the result from multiple linear regression analysis, assurance displayed a coefficient of 0.232 which indicates there is a positive significant relationship between assurance and overall customer satisfaction. The data analysis concludes that assurance is the third most influencing dimension in assessing customer satisfaction when all other dimensions are accounted for.

The result in this study is consistent with a study performed by Verma et al. (2013) where assurance dimension has a directional relationship with customer satisfaction. The result

in the study assessed by Verma et al. (2013) shows that the perceptions of customer were lesser than their expectation, causing the customers to be dissatisfied with the service provided by the transportation company. Barabino et al. (2012) justified that more attention should be emphasized on the improvement of assurance-related items such driver's ability and the courtesy and knowledge of staff are highly correlated with customer satisfaction.

Empathy

According to the data analysis above, empathy has a significant positive relationship with overall customer satisfaction. With reference to the result from Pearson correlation analysis, empathy displayed a correlation of 0.565 with the overall customer satisfaction which indicates a relationship with moderate strength among other dimensions. With the reference to the result from Multiple Linear Regression analysis, empathy displayed a coefficient of 0.210 which indicates there is a positive significant relationship between empathy and overall customer satisfaction. The data analysis concludes that empathy is the fourth most influencing dimension in assessing customer satisfaction when all other dimensions are accounted for.

The result in this study can be supported by a study conducted by Lwesya and Jaffu (2017) where empathy dimension has a significant positive relationship with customer satisfaction. Abdul Quddus and Hudrasyah (2014) also emphasized that the empathy of staff should be paid more attention because each of the dimension in service quality may have different importance and may have different impact on customer satisfaction. Radam et al. (2014) stated that empathy dimension has the potential to increase customer satisfaction value by implementing service quality improvement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study attempts to evaluate how tourists respond to the service provided by Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. While there are several research frameworks that can evaluate the study of customer satisfaction, this study has adopted the framework from Parasuraman et al (1988) which is the SERVQUAL dimension.

Based on the findings in this study, there is a positive and significant relationship between the dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction on the patronage of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. This study also able to identify the variables that affect customer satisfaction. The first objective of this study has been examined where fifteen (15) attributes have been identified to assess the customer satisfaction towards tourist patronage of Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur. The second objective of this study has revealed that tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy have positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction. The third objective of this study has revealed that tangibility, reliability, assurance, and empathy are the most influencing dimension towards customer satisfaction while responsiveness has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction, but it is insignificant.

Within the five dimensions in service quality, assurance dimension has the highest mean score of 12.03 among other dimensions which the respondents were very satisfied on the assurance provided by Hop-On Hop-Off Tour Bus service in Kuala Lumpur, followed by responsiveness with a mean of 11.17 which is the second highest mean score, reliability with a mean of 10.31 which is the third highest mean score, tangibility with a mean of 10.03 which the fourth highest mean score, and lastly empathy with a mean of 9.91 which is the lowest mean score of all dimension. The mean score in assurance indicates that the respondents were satisfied with the assurance provided by the driver and conductor such as politeness and courtesy, knowledge, and driving skills. The mean score in responsiveness indicates that the respondents were satisfied with the response given by the organization and staff such as communication, willingness, and timely and efficient service. The mean score in reliability indicates that the respondents were satisfied with the reliability presented such as ticketing and billing services, punctuality, and safety. The mean score in tangibility indicates that the

respondents were satisfied with facilities provided such as bus station, seats, and cleanliness. The mean score in empathy indicates that the respondents were satisfied with empathy given by the organization and staff such as operating hours, customer requests, and special care.

In this study, the findings revealed a significant relationship between service quality and customers satisfaction. In terms of the significance of dimensions on customer satisfaction, tangibility dimension has the most significant impact on customer satisfaction, followed by reliability, assurance, empathy, and lastly responsiveness.

Recommendation for future research

Due to the limitations encountered in this study, it is encouraged for this study to be conducted in a longer time frame, for instance twelve months. A longer time frame would allow the research to be performed accurately and to increase the number of samples collected for more reliable data analysis. Future research may expand the coverage at Penang because the Hop-On Hop-Off service is also available in Penang Island. It would be a good opportunity to conduct a research in two place and analyze them together. Furthermore, future research should include the study of expectation to evaluate the gap between expectation and perception because this type of study allows researchers to see a clear picture of the differences in expectation and perception.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Quddus, F.S. & Hudrasyah, H., (2014). The influence of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in PT. JNE North Bandung area. *Journal of Business and Management*, 3(5), pp.546-56.
- Abdullah, S., Razak, A.A., Marzuki, A. & Jaafar, M., (2013). Assessing Tourist Satisfaction with the Facilities Provided at Langkawi Island Gateway Jetty Terminals. *Liburna*, 2(2), pp.73-92.
- Abenzoza, R.F., Cats, O. & Susilo, Y.O., (2017). Travel Satisfaction with Public Transport: Determinants, User Classes, Regional Disparities and their Evolution. *Transportation Research Part A*, 95, pp.64-84.
- Agyapong, G.K.Q., (2011). The Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in the Utility Industry – A Case of Vodafone (Ghana). *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(5), pp.203-10.
- Albalate, D. & Bel, G., (2010). Tourism and Urban Public Transport: Holding Demand Pressure Under Supply Constraints. *Tourism Management*, 31, pp.425-33.
- Alsaqre, O.Z.E., (2011). *Investigating the effects of tangible and intangible factors on customers' perceived service quality and loyalty in hotel industry in Al-Ladhiqiyah, Syria*. [Online] Available at: <http://www2.unwto.org/agora/investigating-effects-tangible-and-intangible-factors-customers-perceived-service-quality-and-> [Accessed 2 November 2018].
- Andaleeb, S.S. & Conway, C., (2006). Customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry: an examination of the transaction-specific model. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 20(1), pp.3-11.
- Atiyah, L.A., (2017). Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 11(5), pp.20-28.
- Bajada, T. & Titheridge, H., (2017). The Attitudes of Tourists Towards a Bus Service: Implications for Policy from a Maltese Case Study. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 25, pp.4110-29.
- Bakti, I.G.M.Y. & Sumaedi, S., (2015). P-TRANSQUAL: a service quality model of public land transport services. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 32(6), pp.534-58.
- Barabino, B., Deiana, E. & Tilocca, P., (2012). Measuring service quality in urban bus transport: a modified SERVQUAL approach. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 4(3), pp.238-52.
- Barsky, J.D., (1992). Customer Satisfaction in the Hotel Industry: Meaning and Measurement. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 16(1), pp.51-73.
- Bates, J., Polak, J., Jones, P. & Cook, A., (2001). The valuation of reliability for personal travel. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 37(2-3), pp.191-229.

Beiske, B., (2002). *Research methods. Uses and limitations of questionnaires, interviews, and case studies*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.grin.com/document/15458> [Accessed 15 Oct 2018].

Berry, L.L., Zeithaml, V.A. & Parasuraman, A., (1985). Quality counts in services, too. *Business Horizons*, 28(3), pp.44-52.

Bhattacharya, T., Brown, J., Jaroszynski, M. & Batuhan, T., (2014). The Effects of Perception vs. “Reality” on Travel Behavior after a Major Transit Service Change: The Case of Tallahassee, Florida. *Journal of Public Transportation*, 17(2), pp.1-26.

Bielen, F. & Demoulin, N., (2007). Waiting time influence on the satisfaction-loyalty relationship in services. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, 17(2), pp.174-93.

Blose, J.E. & Tankersley, W.B., (2004). Linking Dimensions of Service Quality to Original Outcomes. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 14(1), pp.75-89.

Boslaugh, S.E., (2010). Secondary Data Source. In N.J. Salkind, ed. *Encyclopedia of Research Design*. SAGE.

Bryman, A. & Bell, E., (2007). *Business Research Methods*. 2nd ed. New York: Oxford University Press Inc.

Chan, L.L. & Idris, N., (2017). Validity and Reliability of The Instrument Using Exploratory Factor Analysis and Cronbach’s alpha. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(10), pp.400-10.

Cheng, J.-H., Lai, C.Y., Chen, H.-P. & Ou, C.-L., (2010). The service quality analysis of public transportation system using PZB model — Dynamic bus information system. In *The 40th International Conference on Computers & Industrial Engineering.*, 2010.

Chong, K.L., (2016). The Impact of Traffic Congestion on Tourist Behaviour: Case Study of Chiang Mai. In *Proceedings of the 14th ApacChrie Conference 2016*. Bangkok, 2016. Dusit Thani College Thailand.

City of Helsinki, (2015). *Light Rail: Public Transport for the Future Helsinki*. [Online] Available at: https://www.hel.fi/hel2/ksv/julkaisut/esitteet/esite_2015-5_en.pdf [Accessed 17 September 2018].

Creswell, J.W., (2003). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications.

Currie, C. & Falconer, P., (2014). Maintaining Sustainable Island Destinations in Scotland: The Role of the Transport-Tourism Relationship. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 3(3), pp.162-72.

Demir, A., Talaat, K. & Aydinli, C., (2015). The Relations among Dimensions of Service Quality, Satisfaction, Loyalty, and Willingness to pay more: Case of GSM Operators Service at Northern-Iraq. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 5(4), pp.146-54.

Dubois, D. & Aliaga, A., (2014). Tourism and Public Transport: A Winning Team? How French and European Transport Authorities Manage Tourist Flows. Frankfurt, Germany, 2014.

Eboli, L. & Mazzulla, G., (2008). A Stated Preference Experiment for Measuring Service Quality in Public Transport. *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 31(5), pp.509-23.

Field, A., (2009). Everything you ever wanted to know about statistics (well, sort of). In *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS*. Third Edition ed. SAGE Publications. pp.31-60.

Friman, M. & Felleson, M., (2009). Service Supply and Customer Satisfaction in Public Transportation: The Quality Paradox. *Journal of Public Transportation*, 12(4), pp.57-69.

Govender, J.P. & Naidu, K., (2011). Evaluating Service Quality in the Durban Freight Transportation Industry. *Journal of Transport and Supply Chain Management*, 5(1), pp.108-22.

Grönroos, C., (1990). *Service Management and Marketing: Managing the Moments of Truth in Service Competition*. Lexington, Massachusetts: Lexington Books.

Hair, J.F.J., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J. & Anderson, R.E., (2009). Multiple Regression Analysis. In *Multivariate Data Analysis*. Seventh Edition ed. Harlow, UK: Pearson. pp.151-230.

Hall, D.R., (1999). Conceptualising tourism transport: inequality and externality issues. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 7(3), pp.181-88.

Halsall, D.A., (2001). Railway heritage and the tourist gaze: Stoomtram Hoorn–Medemblik. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 9(2), pp.151-60.

Handrinos, M.C., Folinas, D. & Rotsios, K., (2015). Using the SERVQUAL model to evaluate the quality of services for a farm school store. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Behaviour in Emerging Markets*, 1(1), pp.62-74.

Hellén, K. & Gummerus, J., (2013). Re-investigating the nature of tangibility/intangibility and its influence on consumer experiences. *Journal of Service Management*, 24(2), pp.130-50.

Hoffman, K.D. & Bateson, J.E.G., (2006). *Services marketing : concepts, strategies & cases*. 3rd ed. Mason, Ohio: Thomson /South-Western.

Holweg, M., (2005). The three dimensions of responsiveness. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 25(7), pp.603-22.

Horsu, E.N. & Yeboah, S.T., (2015). Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction: A Study of Minicab Taxi Services in Cape Coast, Ghana. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(5), pp.1451-64.

Iles, R., (2005). *Public Transport in Developing Countries*. London: Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

Ilieska, K., (2013). Customer Satisfaction Index – as a Base for Strategic Marketing Management. *Journal of Association for Information Communication Technology, Education and Science*, 2(4), pp.327-31.

Irfan, S.M., Kee, M.H.D. & Shahbaz, S., (2012). Service Quality and Rail Transport in Pakistan: A Passenger Perspective. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 18(3), pp.361-69.

Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia, (2018). *Population Quick Info*. [Online] Available at: <http://pqi.stats.gov.my/searchBI.php?tahun=2018&kodData=2&kodJadual=1&kodCiri=4&kodNegeri=Semua> [Accessed 18 September 2018].

Johnston, R., (1995). The determinants of service quality: satisfiers and dissatisfiers. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 6(5), pp.53-71.

Johnston, R., (1997). Identifying the critical determinant of service quality in retail banking: importance and effect. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 15(4), pp.111-16.

Jun, L. & He, G., (2007). Study on Railway Transport Service Quality Evaluation. In *2007 International Conference on Wireless Communications, Networking and Mobile Computing.*, 2007. IEEE.

Kaliannan, M., Puteh, F. & Dorasamy, M., (2014). Measuring Service Quality in Malaysian Local Government: The SERVQUAL Approach. In *Knowledge Management International Conference (KMICe)*. Langkawi, 2014.

Khatri, P.V. & Damodariya, S.M., (2015). Literature Review on Feasibility Study of City Bus Service in Godhra City. *International Journal for Scientific Research & Development*, 3(1), pp.130-33.

Kim, Y.K. & Lee, H.R., (2011). Customer satisfaction using low cost carriers. *Tourism Management*, 32(2), pp.235-43.

Kotler, P. & Keller, K.L., (2011). *Marketing Management*. 14th ed. Prentice Hall.

Kovačić, M. & Milošević, T., (2016). Interdependence of Transport and Tourism. *Annals of Maritime Studies*, 52(1), pp.99-111.

Lehtinen, U. & Lehtinen, J.R., (1991). Two Approaches to Service Quality Dimensions. *The Service Industries Journal*, 11(3), pp.287-303.

Le-Klähn, D.T. & Hall, M., (2014). Tourist use of public transport at destinations – a review. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 18(8), pp.785-803.

Leonnard, S.E., Comm, M. & Thung, F., (2017). The relationship of service quality, word-of-mouth, and repurchase intention in online transportation services. *Journal of Process Management - New Technologies*, 5(4), pp.30-40.

Liu, Y., Siali, F., Darun, M.R. & Ismail, M.F., (2014). Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: Rapid Kuantan in Kuantan Route, Malaysia. In *Socio-Int 14-International Conference on Social Sciences and Humanities*. Istanbul, Turkey, 2014. OCERINT.

Lwesya, F. & Jaffu, R., (2017). Customer Service Quality Management in Public Transport: The Case of Rail Transport in Tanzania. *International Review*, 3-4, pp.102-17.

Mammadov, R., (2012). The Importance of Transportation in Tourism Sector. In *7th Silk Road International Conference "Challenges and Opportunities of Sustainable Economic Development in Eurasian Countries"*. Tblisi - Batumi, Georgia, 2012.

Mammo, M., (2010). Assessment of Customer Satisfaction in Transportation Service Delivery: The Case of Three Terminals of Anbassa City Bus Service Enterprise. *Ethiopian Journal of Business and Economics*, 1(2), pp.29-69.

Mikhaylov, A., Gumenyuk, I. & Mikhaylov, A., (2015). The SERVQUAL model in measuring service quality of public transportation: evidence from Russia. *Quality - Access to Success*, 16(144), pp.78-83.

Mudenda, C. & Guga, D., (2017). An Assessment of the Relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction-A Case of a Public Passenger Road Transportation Company in Zambia. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 6(2), pp.541-55.

Muhammad, A., (2017). An Overview of Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty; a Literature Review. *Austin Journal of Business Administration and Management*, 1(4), p.1020.

NCSS Statistical Software, (2018). *Factor Analysis*. [Online] Available at: https://ncss-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/themes/ncss/pdf/Procedures/NCSS/Factor_Analysis.pdf [Accessed 26 November 2018].

Nutsugbodo, R.Y., (2013). Tourists' perceptions of the quality of public transportation services in the Accra metropolis: a Servqual approach. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 2(4), pp.1-8.

Ojo, T.K., Mireku, D.O., Dauda, S. & Nutsogbodo, R.Y., (2014). Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction of Public Transport on Cape Coast-Accra Route, Ghana. *Developing Country Studies*, 4(18), pp.142-49.

Pallant, J.F., (2007). Checking the reliability of a scale. In *SPSS survival manual : a step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS for Windows (Version 15)*. 3rd ed. Crows Nest, New South Wales: Allen & Unwin. pp.95-99.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. & Berry, L.L., (1985). A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), pp.41-50.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. & Berry, L.L., (1988). SERVQUAL: A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), pp.12-40.

Pearce, P.L., (1985). A Systematic Comparison of Travel-Related Roles. *Human Relations*, 38(1), pp.1001-11.

Peppers, D. & Rogers, M., (2011). *Managing Customer Relationships: A Strategic Framework*. 2nd ed. Wiley.

Persaud, N., (2010). Primary Data Source. In N.J. Salkind, ed. *Encyclopedia of Research Design*. SAGE.

Phongsamran, S. & Uttamang, D., (2016). Service Quality for Ocean Freight Transportation Maersk Line (Thailand) Ltd. *International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science*, 2(1), pp.42-45.

Pizam, A. & Ellis, T., (1999). Customer satisfaction and its measurement in hospitality enterprises. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 11(7), pp.326-39.

Purcărea, V.L., Gheorghe, I.R. & Petrescu, C.M., (2013). The Assessment of Perceived Service Quality of Public Health Care Services in Romania Using the SERVQUAL Scale. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 6, pp.573-85.

Rajamani, A. & Rizal, P., (2013). Role Of Transportation In Tourism Industry In Sikkim State, India. *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*, 2(6), pp.336-46.

Ramees, R.M. & Safeena, P.K., (2016). Customer Needs and Customer Satisfaction. In *A Capacity Building Training Programme Equipping the Fisher women Youth for the Future*.

Rietveld, P., Bruinsma, F.R. & Vuuren, D.J.v., (2001). Coping with unreliability in public transport chains: A case study for Netherlands. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 35(6), pp.539-59.

Sam, E.F., Hamidu, O. & Daniels, S., (2018). SERVQUAL analysis of public bus transport services in Kumasi metropolis, Ghana: Core user perspectives. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 6(1), pp.25-31.

Setyowati, , (2016). Innovation of Service Quality in City Bus Transportation. In *Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Public Management (ICPM 2016)*., 2016. Atlantis Press.

So, S.-h., Kim, J., Cheong, K. & Cho, G., (2006). Evaluating the service quality of third-party logistics service providers using the analytic hierarchy process. *Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, 3(3), pp.261-70.

Sorupia, E., (2005). Rethinking the Role of Transportation in Tourism., 2005.

Sureshchandar, G.S., Rajendran, C. & Anantharaman, R.N., (2002). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction—a factor specific approach. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 16(4), pp.363-79.

Su, M.M. & Wall, G., (2009). The Qinghai-Tibet Railway and Tibet Tourism: Travelers' Perspectives. *Tourism Management*, 30(5), pp.650-57.

Taherdoost, H., Sahibuddin, S. & Jalaliyoon, N., (2014). *Exploratory Factor Analysis; Concepts and Theory*. [Online] Available at: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/1bd8/bbd66524ccf605c879982cd35ef3a3d52160.pdf> [Accessed 26 November 2018].

Tavakol, M. & Dennick, R., (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 2, pp.53-55.

Thompson, K. & Schofield, P., (2002). The Dimensions of Quality of Urban Public Transport-An Overseas Visitor Perspective on Greater Manchester. *Tourism Destination Planning*, 42, pp.281-81.

Thompson, K. & Schofield, P., (2007). An investigation of the relationship between public transport performance and destination satisfaction. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 15(2), pp.136-44.

Turnquist, M.A., (1981). Strategies for Improving Reliability of Bus Transit Service. *Transportation Research Record*, pp.7-13.

Turnquist, M.A. & Blume, S.W., (1980). Evaluating Potential Effectiveness of Headway Control Strategies for Transit Systems. *Transportation Research Record*, 746, pp.25-29.

Tzeng, G.-H. & Chang, H.-F., (2011). Applying Importance-Performance Analysis as a Service Quality Measure in Food Service Industry. *Journal of Technology Management & Innovation*, 6(3), pp.106-15.

Verma, M., Verma, A., Ajith, P. & Sindhe, S., (2014). Urban bus transport service quality and sustainable development: understanding the service gaps. *Indian Journal of Transport Management*, 38(2), pp.98-112.

Vilakazi, A.M. & Govender, K.K., (2014). Exploring Bus Service Quality in South Africa: A Structural Equation Modelling Approach. *Journal of Transport and Supply Chain Management*, 8(1), pp.1-10.

Williams, B., Brown, T. & Onsmann, A., (2010). Exploratory factor analysis: A five-step guide for novices. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, 8(3), pp.1-13.

Wilson, A., Zeithaml, V.A., Bitner, M.J. & Gremler, D.D., (2008). *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus Across the Firm*. London: McGraw-Hill.

Zakaria, Z., Hussin, Z.H., Abdul Batau, M.F. & Zakaria, Z., (2010). Service Quality of Malaysian Public Transports: A Case Study in Malaysia. *Cross-Cultural Communication*, 6(2), pp.84-92.

Zeithaml, V.A., Bitner, M.J. & Gremler, D.D., (2006). *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus Across the Firm*. 4th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.

Zeithaml, V.A., Bitner, M.J. & Gremler, D.D., (2017). *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus Across the Firm*. Seventh Edition ed. McGraw-Hill Education.